

Mass-Energy Equivalence derived from Work and Kinetic Energy

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Abstract: Relativistic energy is concerned with the motion of bodies whose velocities approach the speed of light. Also, kinetic energy is a form of energy that quantifies the work performed by an object due to its motion. This paper presents an equation of mass-energy equivalence derived from the work-kinetic energy.

Keywords: relativistic energy, differential equation, speed of light

1. Introduction

The equation of Einstein's mass-energy equivalence [1-4] is $E = mc^2$, where E , m , and c denote electromagnetic/light energy, mass, and speed of light respectively. The derivation of the equations of relativistic mass [5-8] and mass-energy equivalence is obtained from the work and kinetic energy by differentiation and integration [9].

2. Work-Kinetic Energy Relation

The total work (dW) is done when a force (F) is applied to a particle with mass (m) and the particle is moved through a distance (ds). The equation for the work done is given below:

$$dW = Fds$$

According to Newton's second law of motion, we rewrite the equation as follows:

$$dW = Fds = m \frac{dv}{dt} ds = m \frac{ds}{dt} dv$$
$$dW = mv dv \quad (1)$$

By differentiating the kinetic energy (E) = $\frac{1}{2}mv^2$ with respect to time, we get

$$\frac{dE}{dt} = \frac{1}{2} \left(m2v \frac{dv}{dt} \right)$$
$$dE = mv dv \quad (2)$$

From the equations (1) and (2), we obtain

$$dW = dE = mv dv, \text{ which is a differential equation [9].}$$

By integrating this differential equation, we get the equation of kinetic energy:

$$\int_0^W dW = \int_0^E dE = \int_0^v mv dv$$

$$W = E = \frac{1}{2}mv^2$$

The work energy, therefore, is equal to the kinetic energy.

3. Relativistic Energy

The equation of relativistic mass states that $m = \frac{m_0}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}$.

Squaring both sides of this equation:

$$m^2 = \frac{m_0^2}{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \Rightarrow m^2(c^2 - v^2) = m_0^2c^2, \text{ where rest mass energy} = m_0^2c^2$$

$$m^2c^2 - m^2v^2 = m_0^2c^2$$

By differentiating the equation with respect to time, we get

$$2mc^2 \frac{dm}{dt} - 2mv \frac{d(mv)}{dt} = 0 \Rightarrow c^2 \frac{dm}{dt} = v \frac{d(mv)}{dt}$$

$$\frac{dE}{dt} = Fv = v \frac{d(mv)}{dt} = c^2 \frac{dm}{dt}$$

$$dE = c^2 dm$$

$$\int_0^K dK = \int_{m_0}^m c^2 dm$$

$$K = c^2(m - m_0), \text{ where } K \text{ is kinetic energy.}$$

$$\text{Total Energy (} E \text{)} = \text{Kinetic Energy (} K \text{)} + \text{Rest Mass-Energy (} m_0c^2 \text{)}$$

$$E = c^2(m - m_0) + m_0c^2$$

$$E = c^2m - c^2m_0 + m_0c^2$$

$$E = mc^2$$

Einstein mass-energy equivalence denotes the relativistic energy.

4. Conclusion

The mass-energy equivalence along with relativistic mass and energy play an important role in the Einstein's theory of special relativity. Also, the relativistic mechanics is concerned with the motion of bodies whose velocities approach the speed of light. In this article, the equation of Einstein's mass-energy equivalence has been derived from work-kinetic energy relation.

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